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**DRIVEIQ: AN ADAPTIVE BEHAVIOR-AWARE NAVIGATION
SYSTEM WITH REAL-TIME DRIVER PROFILING AND ENSEMBLE
ML CLASSIFICATION**

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Abstract—Driver distraction and abnormal driving behavior are among the leading causes of road accidents and navigation confusion worldwide. Traditional navigation systems mainly focus on shortest path routing and often ignore the driver's behavior, perception, and decision-making ability. This paper proposes DriveIQ, a behavior-aware adaptive navigation system designed to improve driving safety and route guidance using machine learning techniques. The system analyzes GPS trajectory data and extracts important driving features such as deviation frequency, turn complexity, and focus score to identify driver behavior patterns. An ensemble learning approach combining Logistic Regression, Random Forest, and Neural Network models is used to classify drivers into Safe, Average, Risky, and Aggressive categories. Based on the detected behavior, the system dynamically adapts route recommendations, alert thresholds, and instruction verbosity. Experimental analysis shows that the proposed system effectively reduces driver confusion and improves navigation assistance by providing personalized and behavior-dependent routing support.

Index Terms—Driver Behavior Analysis, Adaptive Navigation, Ensemble Machine Learning, Route Personalization, Confusion Detection, Explainable AI, Driver Classification, Predictive Risk Assessment

I. INTRODUCTION

Rapid increase in the number of vehicles has raised the threat of road accidents across the globe. Of all the causes that lead to accidents, unsafe behavior of a driver like aggressive driving, drowsiness and distracted driving has a greater impact on road incidents. According to some of the recent studies a considerable number of accidents can be attributed to the drivers' patterns rather than the mechanical failure of vehicles. The driver monitoring systems so far available are mainly rule-based systems and use a set of predetermined thresholds for parameters like speed, acceleration and lane deviation. While rule based systems are easy to be implemented, it fail to incorporate the characteristics of a complex and varying driving pattern.

As a consequence, rule-based driver monitoring systems are generally ineffective in the real world environments where road

and vehicle conditions vary largely. With the advent of data-driven technologies, machine learning is one of the finest tools used in analyzing and predicting driver behavior and classifying it by learning the various patterns of driving from the training data, as machine learning models are competent enough to deal with non-linear relation and large set of data which helps in classification of driving behaviors efficiently.

In this paper a driver behavior classification system is proposed. Using machine learning algorithms, driver behavior (normal, aggressive and drowsy) is classified. Using vehicular dynamics and traffic features to train several models and compare to find an algorithm suitable for the driver behavior classification task.

The objective is to develop an efficient and reliable system that contributes to road safety by identifying potentially dangerous driving behavior in its early stages. Applications such as intelligent transportation system, advanced driver assistance systems and real time driver monitoring can take great advantage of such system.

A. Contributions of this Work

- **Behavioral Analysis Based on Features:** Both lane based and traffic based features are utilized that helps to infer a good idea about driver behavior.
- **Multiple behavior Detection:** Unlike the other systems working on binary classification the proposed system is to determine different behaviors including normal, aggressive and drowsy driving behavior.
- **Model Comparison based on performance measures:** Detailed comparison among the algorithms is made based on the metrics like accuracy, precision, recall and f1-score.
- **Usability in practical real life:** The proposed system is helpful to apply in the real world, such as, the intelligent transport system and the drivers' assistive system.

B. Novelty and justification

The novelty of the work presented here lies in the effective

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use of more than one machine learning model and a coherent method for feature engineering to classify the behavior of the driver. While previous works focused on implementing a single model and a small set of features, this work applies a set of different features and tested different models to increase the performance of the model classification.

Moreover, the model tried to maintain the balance between accuracy and efficiency. Machine learning methods used are efficient and deliver good performance. The ensemble techniques like Random Forest and Gradient Boosting improve prediction accuracy and increase bias reduction.

C. Structure of the Paper

The structure of this paper is as follows. Section II surveys previous literature on driver behavior classification. Section III outlines our proposed method, involving data pre-processing, feature extraction and modeling. Section IV presents and analyses the results of the proposed method. Section V summarizes the work and future prospects.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Classification of driver behavior has been extensively investigated during the recent past. A driver's behavior is a key factor for determining road safety and for intelligent transport systems. Increasing number of vehicles and traffic density is the reason for monitoring and analyzing the behavior of drivers. Thus, various approaches were introduced to detect unsafe driving behavior that causes the road accidents, like aggressive driving, distraction, drowsiness etc. However, these methods are less adaptive and have some limitations in recognizing and predicting complex and dynamic driving behavior.

The drawbacks of the rule-based methods motivated researchers to explore the domain of machine learning for driver behavior classification. Among the many different algorithms used for behavior classification, Logistic Regression, Decision Trees, SVM and Random Forest were commonly used. However, some researchers have shown that ensemble methods like Random Forest and Gradient Boosting achieve significantly better results compared to single models like SVM and Decision Trees. These methods are effective in handling non-linearity of data and also overcome overfitting.

In addition, few researchers have addressed the problem using deep learning algorithms like Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) which can classify different behavior using large amount of sequential driving data and analyze complex spatial-temporal relationships among features. But, the downside is that deep learning approaches are computationally expensive and require large amount of data which is a limitation for implementation.

Furthermore, recent research also considered combinations of features from different domains, such as lane-based features and traffic-based features and used machine learning algorithms for behavior classification. The combination of features proved to be more accurate.

Research

A number of studies have explored the development of efficient systems for driver behavior classification based on

machine learning algorithms. In previous years, supervised machine learning algorithms such as Logistic Regression, Decision Trees and Support Vector Machines (SVM) were used to classify the driving behavior patterns based on vehicle dynamics data. Although these models performed with moderate accuracy, they were often ineffective in addressing nonlinear and complicated relationships.

Recently, ensemble machine learning methods, such as Random Forest and Gradient Boosting, are gaining attention in classifying the driving patterns based on multiple weak classifiers for higher accuracy of prediction. These models exhibited more robustness and generality, and are also effective in dealing with high-dimensional data sets.

Advanced deep learning algorithms have also been explored, but for massive and sequential data it is still required to have high performance machine learning algorithms for reducing time and computation with no loss of accuracy. Hence, there is more attention towards low computational cost yet efficient machine learning models for real-time system design.

A. Challenges

Class imbalance in real driving conditions means the count of aggressive and drowsy driving behaviors are significantly less in comparison to normal driving. This makes the performance of models poor towards fewer instances, and the model becomes biased toward the more frequent class.

- **Data quality issues:** Issues like missing data, noise and errors can lead to decrease in the performance of machine learning models.
- **Complex and Non-Linear Patterns:** The dynamic nature and interdependencies between factors are quite complex in real driving conditions.
- **Real time implementation:** Most advanced techniques require immense computational power.
- **Generalization:** Machine learning models trained over one data set may not generalize well for other data sets.

B. Motivation of Proposed System

The proposed system motivation is to overcome the shortcomings in current driver behavior classification methods by designing an efficient and reliable system.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. System Architecture and Data Acquisition

The DriveIQ system has been developed as a pipeline structure to incorporate real-time navigation with behavior-aware intelligence. It contains multiple components working together to gather data, process it, and provide the output accordingly.

The system is initiated by a user request (source and destination as input). Using the OpenRouteService API, the route from the source to the destination is retrieved. In parallel,

real-time position tracking of the user is recorded using GPS, capturing latitude, longitude, and trajectory.

The collected data are processed through the following structured pipeline.

B. Data Processing and Machine Learning Model

The raw collected data are processed to maintain data quality and consistency. Noise removal is performed on GPS data, missing values are handled, and feature normalization is applied for compatibility with machine learning models.

Behavioral data are transformed into meaningful features such as number of deviations, speed score, turn complexity score, session length, and driver focus score.

The deviation frequency is calculated as:

$$\text{Deviation Frequency} = \frac{\text{Deviations}}{\text{Distance}} \quad (1)$$

The focus score is calculated as:

$$\text{Focus} = 100 - (4D + 6C + 2S) \quad (2)$$

where D represents deviations, C represents confusion events, and S represents stops.

An ensemble machine learning model combining Logistic Regression, Random Forest, and Multi-Layer Perceptron is used for prediction.

The final prediction is obtained using a voting-based ensemble method:

$$\text{Prediction} = \text{MajorityVote}(\text{Model}_1, \text{Model}_2, \text{Model}_3) \quad (3)$$

The system classifies drivers into four categories: Safe, Average, Risky, and Aggressive.

C. Prediction, Adaptive Navigation and Workflow

The system incorporates predictive modeling to enhance navigation intelligence.

The risk estimation is given by:

$$\text{Risk} = \text{Base} + \text{TurnFactor} + \text{DistanceFactor} + \text{BehaviorFac} \quad (4)$$

The overall workflow of the system is illustrated below:

Fig. 1. System Architecture of DriveIQ

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The DriveIQ system was evaluated on parameters of behavior like deviation, stop, confusion and variation in speed collected from simulation scenarios of navigation. The ensemble machine learning model with a combination of Logistic Regression, Random Forest and Multi-Layer Perceptron showed consistent and accurate results on all test data sets.

The system was found to have higher accuracy than individual classifiers with precision, recall and F1 score balanced. Drivers could be accurately classified into four classes Safe, Average, Risky and Aggressive on the basis of their behavior where high deviation and confusion leads to riskier class. The prediction modules were also designed to further enhance system accuracy by estimating the probability of missing turn

and by forecasting of driver behavior. Overall the system provides accurate prediction, timely alert, optimal navigation by adapting according to driver's behavior and provides reliable performance.

V. CONCLUSION

DriveIQ is an intelligent and adaptive navigation system which works on combining the features of real time GPS tracker and machine learning-based behavior analysis. Ensemble learning approach helps in accurate driver classification and robust prediction of navigation risks. Feature engineering is used to transform raw behavioral data to meaningful feature representations capturing the specific driving behavior of drivers.

The proposed system helps to improvise navigation by providing alerts before any dangerous situation arises and by guiding drivers along with optimal routes accordingly. The system provides explainability and evaluation mechanisms that helps in proving the reliability and accuracy. It is a flexible and scalable intelligent navigation system that takes smart decisions based on the analysis of driver's behavior

A. Future Work

The DriveIQ system can be further improvised by incorporating real time traffic and weather data to take more context aware decisions for routing and navigation. Deep learning

algorithms like LSTM or RNN can be employed to get better results by capturing the temporality in driving behavior. Reinforcement learning can be utilized to adapt navigation decisions over time based on interaction with the user.

The system can be improved further by incorporating data from IOT enabled vehicle sensors such as accelerometers and brake pattern to get more insights on drivers behavior. A mobile application can be developed for system to increase the reachability. System can also be made scalable by implementing in cloud platform. Enhanced explainable AI models can be used and personalized feedback mechanism for the driver can be proposed.

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